

IBN KHALDUN AND HIS IMPACT ON HISTORIANS AND REFORMISTS OF THE MODERN ERA THE MAGHREB (THE ARAB MAGHREB AND NORTHWEST AFRICA) DOMAIN

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Abstract

This Study aims to research the impact of Ibn Khaldun's phenomenon (who has gained a constant presence in the community of historians and reformists) on historians, philosophers, and sociologists in later eras, and the dedicated endeavor to demonstrate the characteristics of the work of such community members in the Modern Arab Renaissance Project, based on the history of Ibn Khaldun, his theorizations, approach, and vision, and through the following tracks: (Editing and Use). The Study also examines the historians and reformists' perception of historical events in Ibn Khaldun's historical text and in the approach of his history-based study to transfer them from the sphere of history and undertake an intimate effort of its interpretation so that it will be the force that achieves the desired reform. The importance of the Study is highlighted in the fruitful insight of historians and reformists of the Arab Maghreb to the text of Ibn Khaldun's history and to the text of his *Al Muqaddimah/Introduction* (Ibn Khaldun's Prolegomena), which tends to emphasize the distinctive features of the text to encourage its use and utilization, and it is exactly what we can describe as the "Possession of Historical Knowledge" and its use in an effective way. These historians and reformists are intimately cognizant of the importance of Ibn Khaldun's historical text and its introduction, and the importance of conjuring them up to reproduce them according to an ideology that expresses their intellectual propensity.

Keywords: Ibn Khaldun, The Maghreb, Reform Movements, Renaissance.

INTRODUCTION

In the field of human thought through successive eras, there is a phenomenon –among many phenomena- that attracts attention, and it is the “Phenomenon of Influence and Effect Among Successive Generations”, where the subsequent generation makes its

impact, and also is influenced by the previous one in an effect that is sometimes multidimensional and differs in its fields and varies in its degrees between the two sides of the phenomenon (the Influencer and the Influenced), and where sometimes the influence of the former on the latter is a strong and deep one and to a degree of comprehensiveness that almost does away with the independence and scientific identity of the party affected, and in some other times the influence is weak in its degree and limited in its scope, preserving the individuality of the party affected and the independence of his/her view, and consequently the rates of influence in this case are inconsequential.

Ibn Khaldun is considered as one of the exceptional elites who had a legacy that assisted in weaving important stages of human history. The domain of Ibn Khaldun's works is the domain of history, both in thought and reality, and therefore the works of this historian directly attracted the attention of historians, reformists, and politicians who came after him and helped them in rooting their historical thinking to infer a correct approach to reform behavior.

Ibn Khaldun School between Denial and Proof

The rational-realistic critical rationalism vivified Ibn Khaldun's Introduction as seen by Al-Jabri (Al-Jabri 1993: 43). Ibn Khaldun came to examine the past and to learn lessons and conclusions from an Introduction, which he set up as a lesson for the mind, an example from history, and a statement from the past to the future (Al-Jabri 1993: 43). Al-Jabri believes in his critical reading of Ibn Khaldun's thought that it is impossible to talk about a Khaldun School or intellectual current that originated with Ibn Khaldun and continued to the modern Arab renaissance era, as such current did not exist, and "Khaldunism" in this sense does not make any sense (Al-Jabri 1993: 309). Al-Jabri believes that it is a question of whether we want to affirm the existence of the current of "Khaldunism" in extrapolating our heritage to search for those who touched base with the thought of Ibn Khaldun and sought to develop it, enrich it, and realize it (Al-Jabri 1993: 310). Al-Jabri tries to answer the questions of achieving the goals of "Khaldunism" by way of answering the following query: (Has Ibn Khaldun really become a role model to be looked up to by those who came after him?) (Al-Jabri 1993: 315). According to Bouthoule, it is difficult to know exactly the impact of Ibn Khaldun and the spread of his writings (Bouthoule [d.n]: 124), and if his works had been studied in depth in previous centuries, those studies would have led to many writings and commentaries on them (Bouthoule [d.n]: 124). Bouthoule points out that Ibn Khaldun's approach remained without any footprint after him, and if his writings had existed in other circumstances, the writings of this brilliant pioneer would have prompted the creation of a stand-alone science and would have generated a long series of studies and would have been the starting point for a whole new school. Bouthoule alludes to the non-continuity of the Khaldounian approach among historians and politicians in the following eras until the modern era. The "Introduction" according to Bouthoule, was the end of an era and the beginning of a new one, ***"[t]he last ray emitted by what was rightly called as the 'Arab Renaissance', the torch of which then passed on to Europe."***(Bouthoule [d.n]: 126). The British Orientalist Hamilton Gibb, in his article on the Science of History in the Encyclopedia of Islam, is of the same view in

denying a prevailing tendency that represents the influence of Ibn Khaldun on subsequent historians, especially Egyptian historians, and ***"[t]here is a question that is still obscure from the point of view of the science of recording history among Muslims, and this issue is that there is no evidence that any of the successors of Ibn Khaldun studied or applied the principles that he espoused, despite the flourishing of the school of Egyptian historians in the following centuries."***(JB 1981: 93-94). And according to the Russian Orientalist Vladimir Barthold, the theory of Ibn Khaldun also did not affect other Arab authors (Barthold 1958, 92).

Abdul Wahid Wafi, one of the examiners of the "Introduction", believes that Ibn Khaldun's Introduction did not have the prevalence it deserved after him, and Wafi explains that by stating that Ibn Khaldun was ahead of the thinking of his era by several stages, and that is why, neither his contemporaries nor those who came after him in the subsequent four centuries were able to follow him in his theories and thought (Wafi 1957 p1: 136). In the context of the previous trends, Himmich's questions about the existence of the Khaldounian School come into play and as per the following: (Why did Ibn Khaldun's theoretical work remain almost forgotten for almost six centuries? And did Ibn Khaldun have direct students in his modernist approach?) (Himmich 2001: 14). Himmich believes that our inductive reasoning may face difficulty in searching for students near or even far from Ibn Khaldun's time, prominent commentators and expositors such as Ibn Al-Azraq, Ibn Al-Sakak, or from the nineteenth century such as Al-Salawi. However, these readers of Ibn Khaldun do not express a school that ***"[w]ould have the credit of deepening the teacher's theoretical dedication or providing his great hunches with fecund fields."***(Himmich 2001: 16). According to Branchvik (Branchvik 1988 p2: 411), no rival or successor to him [Ibn Khaldun that is] has emerged up to modern times. One of the most prominent scholars who wrote about this quandary is Al-Azmeh, who proceeds from the criticism that is directed at the origins of the Khaldounian studies, whose vision is based on the "Non-Historicity of History", and that the thought of the modern Arab renaissance is inherent in this vision (Al-Azmeh 1987: 8).

Al-Azmeh believes that the al-ʿIbar Kitab "Book of Lessons" has exceeded its historical limitations in certain historical moments and in the context of efforts of interpretation and the research in the connotations of the Khaldounian text in a manner that is commensurate with those historical moments. Al-Azmeh iterates that the process of interpretation of the al-ʿIbar Kitab "Book of Lessons" was superficial, routine, and regressive, and that the al-ʿIbar Kitab "Book of Lessons" did not receive enough attention from its contemporaries and even from those who came after its issuance (Al-Azmeh 1987: 205). The only exception in this regard according to Al-Azmeh is Ibn Al-Azraq, the Author of "Bada'i' al- Silk fi Taba'i' al-Mulk" (The Marvel of State Conduct, and the Nature of Authority), who was distinguished by his integrative view of the al-ʿIbar Kitab "Book of Lessons" and its Introduction, and who gave a systematic attention to his work. Al-Azmeh decried the so-called "Khaldounian School" in Ottoman history (Al-Azmeh 1987: 205). Al Azmeh mentioned the reasons that may have weakened Ibn Khaldun's influence in his contemporaries and which are related to the schism that Ibn Khaldun caused in the fabric of the well-known models in the structure of the Arab-Islamic heritage and the collision of

this schism with a strong rejection, not to mention being ignored and ridiculed (Al-Azmeh 1987: 226). On the other hand, the Introduction of the al-‘Ibar Kitab "Book of Lessons" gained admiration, and its developed materials were used, which were associated with topics and connotations that did not reflect the impact of the systematic schism that Ibn Khaldun engaged in (Al-Azmeh 1987: 226). Al-Azmeh criticized the historical studies and perspectives in the reading of al-‘Ibar Kitab "Book of Lessons", and stated that the correct approach in reading it is by looking at this book in a historical context and a specific time and place, as ***"[r]arely do we find anyone who views the works of this brilliant thinker as belonging to a certain time and place, to a specific historical experience, and to an inclusion in the intellectual world that is derived from a bygone era."*** (Al-Azmeh 2000: 9). In their reading of Ibn Khaldun, the holders of this trend presented an approach that is based on scientific foundations in directing criticism of the reality of Khaldounian studies, which has become a negative problem facing the researcher seeking to advance the study of Ibn Khaldun, and the researcher in this regard must take into account this inferential fallacies represented by the negative accumulation produced to correct reading behavior in the works of Ibn Khaldun, where a ***"[h]uge accumulation of Khaldounian literature produced east and west, and an image has been formed about Ibn Khaldun, and it has been accepted, and it illustrated the fact that he was the most original thinker among all of our ancient thinkers, and the fact that he was authentic in the sense that his thought has achieved transcendence in relation to the ancient erudition/knowledge system (Episteme), and in some ways it has become contemporary with us."*** (Oumlil 2005: 5).

Ibn Khaldun, Reception and Influence, From His Era to the Modern Arab Renaissance Period

In the context of achieving the reasonableness of history on a practical and cognitive level, the importance of Ibn Khaldun's thought and its value in achieving consciousness, rebirth, identification, and overcoming crises, and its importance to society and the reform movement are all confirmed, as Nassif Nassar stated, quote: ***"[p]ushing forward historical, sociological, and philosophical thought and promoting it."***, unquote, (Nassar 2023: 18). And in the context of determining the relationship of the Khaldounian thought with the reformist current in the Islamic world in the modern era, Ibn Khaldun's position and impact on the thought of Islamic reforms led by the elite in the modern era can also be identified on one hand, while on the other hand, an emphasis is placed on the notion that there was a significant neglect of the Khaldounian thought in the modern reformist discourse, which was particularly adopted by the Revival School (Modern Literary Renaissance), (Machouche 2012: 32-33).

First: The Early Beginnings

Ibn Al-Sakkak Al Miknasi (d. 1415 A.D)

Ibn Khaldun extends the presence of Ibn Al-Sakkak to explain the reasons for the emergence and rise of states and the reasons for their fall, and Ibn Al-Sakkak alludes to luxury and considers it as an indicator and a reason for the beginning of decline and

collapse, and uses the discussions and economic foundations to explain that downfall that results from the increase in the difference between income and expenses and the exhaustion of production revenues through the realization of luxury's objectives. (Ibn Al-Sakkak [d.n], 78) Ibn Khaldun also transfers his theorizations from the imagined to the realistic by representing the history and biography of the Almohad State (A North African Berber Muslim Empire founded in the 12th century), at its beginning and at its ending (Ibn Al-Sakkak [d.n]: 78).

Second: Ibn Khaldun, the Historian of Relapse: "The Jurists and the Historians" in Andalusia as an Example.

1. Ibn Asim (d. 1456 A.D)

Ibn Khaldun was interested in everything in order to change everything, and Muhammad Aziz Al-Hababi believes that Khaldonism should be presented as a living and enriched thought (Al-Hababi 1982: 327), and by extrapolating history, he became a reader of the cracking of the states and a thinker of relapse (Himmich [d.n]: 146), and he became an extraordinary model for the elites who are trying to explain their reality.

One example of whom is Ibn Asim, "The Jurist and the Historian", who witnessed the reality of historical determinism in the context of reading the causes of the collapse of Muslims in Al-Andalus, and whose philosophy of history is based on Islamic foundations that seek to draw lessons from historical events based on Ibn Khaldun and his observation and extrapolation (Abdel Moneim 2019: 118). And Ibn Asim is a living witness to the last days of the fall of Al-Andalus, and in his book, which is similar in its modernity and profundity to Ibn Khaldun, the Khaldounian Induction Method is represented in the interpretation of the history of the Abbasid State (The third Caliphate to succeed the Islamic prophet Muhammad) and through reading that is based on the new Khaldounian historical research tools. Ibn Asim draws on the approach and induction of Ibn Khaldun to address the causes of the decay of states, "***[a]nd this reality for these Abbasid Caliphs emanating from their Turkish allies regarding the fallacies of existence and the horrors of the world, is what was promised by the Prophet (As-Sadiq Al Masdoq) (The one who tells the truth and the narrator and reporter of the truth, respectively), according to Ibn Khaldun's view, and it is also what the extrapolation into the thought of Ibn Khaldun has indicated, and as was narrated at the beginning of his history regarding the states when they reach their natural age. Ergo, whoever wants to, can review their words there, for it is what can be argued against and also what can be attested to, concerning the proof of existence, and 'to Allah belongs the command before and after.'***" (Ibn Asim 1989 p1: 294).

2. Ibn Al-Azraq Muhammad ibn Ali Al-Asbahi (d. 1491 A.D)

Ibn Al-Azraq is a scholar jurist and historian who followed the method of Ibn Khaldun, and his book "Bedai'us-Silk fi Tabai'l-Mülk" (The Marvel of State Conduct, and the Nature of Authority) was noted for its modernity and seriousness by Al-Maqqarī Al-Tilmisānī and Aḥmad Bābā Al-Timbuktī, and this Ibn Al-Azraq's book is wonderful in its subject -as its readers attested to- and in it, he [Ibn Al Azraq that is] summarized the "Introduction" to

Ibn Khaldun's history of the Kitab al-ʿIbar "Book of Lessons", and added many useful additions to it (Ibn Al-Azraq 1999 p1: 40), and he presented his multiple theories, and organized some of these theories systematically, and took from the "Introduction" multiple texts and explained them (Ibn Al-Azraq 2008 p1: 26). The rediscovery of Ibn Al-Azraq and his influence on the Renaissance Thought in the Al-Maghreb Al-Arabi, came when Ibn Khaldun's thought continued through Ibn Al-Azraq's students (Grissa 2006: 65). And with a strong Islamic spirit, a new trend has emerged in the history of the modern awakening of the Al-Maghreb Al-Arabi, calling for new reform and the modernization of military structures to stand up to foreign concessions. (Al-Manūnī 1973 p1: 264-273).

Third: Interpretation of the History of the Al Maghreb Al Arabi Based on the Term "Khaldounian Asabiyyah (Tribalism)"

Arafa Al-Shabi (1473-1542 A.D), Al-Diwani (in the Seventeenth Century)

For Ibn Khaldun, "Al Asabiyyah" or (Tribalism), as Mohammed Aziz Al-Hababi sees it, represented for the all-encompassing Maghreb society, the driver of political and social history within the tribal centralization that governed the structure of the state (Boutaleb 2006: 4). Hamed Ibn Sharifa pointed out that Ibn Khaldun's theory in the fourteenth century A.D about "Tribal Asabiyyah" is still a relatively persistent feature between the individual and the sheikh (leader) of the group or the domain, in the western Tunisian center at the end of the eighteenth-century A.D (Khadija 2018: 38). The most prominent example of historians and politicians, who sought to benefit from the Maghreb history based on the dictionary of Ibn Khaldun's techniques, specifically his unique vocabulary "Al Asabiyyah", is Al Shabi, the founder of the young emirate "Al Shabiya", who chronicled the tribes' relentless pursuit in history to sharpen the theory of history to Ibn Khaldun, and ***"[a]ccording to the law that Ibn Khaldun extrapolated from the biography of the Arab and Berber tribes, the "Hanansheh" (Ancient Arab Tribe in the Maghreb) were able by virtue of the power of their Tribal Asabiyyah and the scope of their influence to bring the tribes neighboring them under their control, and the Al Shabiya benefited from this alliance since the Hanansheh fell under their influence."***

(Al-Shabi 1982, 75). Al-Shabi presents Ibn Khaldun's theories on the end of "Al Asabiyyah", and this is consistent with the law that he derived from Ibn Khaldun in his talk about the stability of the state and the possibility of dispensing with "Al Asabiyyah", (Al-Shabi 1982, 122). Another example of the seventeenth-century scholars is the historian Al-Idwani, who sought to devote Bedouinism to explaining the deterioration of the economic, political, social, and moral life in the Maghreb (Al-Idwani 1996: 47-49).

Fourth: Al-Hasan Al-Yusi (1636-1691, A.D) [Al Khalduni] and "Lectures"

In his lectures, Al-Yusi gives a vivid and talking picture of the vast Maghreb that he lived in and was contemporaneous with (Al-Harari 1980: 22). He suffered from the experience of the Fez Civilization and its structure of luxury and its attached accessories (Al-Fassi 1979: 177). He adopted ideas that are considered revolutionary in nature relative to the thinking that prevailed during his time. His scientific interests can be found in his writings and letters on social issues in the reality of the Baadiyah (Desert Environment) and the

Metropolis (Zamamah 1979: 390). Al-Yusi's observation of the social phenomenon of his time, including the economic conditions of society, the aspirations of people and their daily living problems (Al-Khattabi 1979, No. 31: 33), and his reflections on the social issues that were abound in his lectures and in which he presented the affairs of his time (AL-Khattabi 1979: Edition No. 15: 137), and his contact with the Baadiyah, all made him more aware of the structures and contents of the Maghreb society, and he may have underscored Ibn Khaldun's echoes when he embarked on comparing and contrasting the natures of Bedouins and city dwellers (Zanbir 1979: 276).

In the course of giving his lectures, Al-Yusi conveyed valuable ideas worthy of consideration that reflected the influence of Ibn Khaldun in them and encompassed in such ideas the perspective of the author of the "Introduction" in the code of human assembly and in the renaissance of society and its civilization (Al-Fassi 1979: Edition No. 15: 29-30) (Al-Yusi 2006: p1: 37-38). On the other hand, we see the influence of Ibn Khaldun on Al-Yusi through his political view of justice and governance and its forms, in the context of a historical seminal moment in which the Maghreb started in earnest to look forward to achieving national unity. (Al-Kettani 1979: 199-203).

Fifth: The Phenomenon of "Al-Takmeel" (The Completion) Al Saghir Bin Yusuf Al-Baji (1694-1770 A.D) (as an example)

There are many forms of editing and using Ibn Khaldun's Introduction and history that ranged between: Al-Naqd (Criticism) (Al-Siddiq 1347: A.H), Al-Tamtheel and Al-Sharh (Representation and Explanation) (Al-Khourī 1877: Historical Section: 208), Al-Ikhtisar (Abbreviation) (Khoja [d.n]: 195-196), and Al-Takmeel (Completion), and one of the most prominent examples of historians who sought to complement the Kitab al-'Ibar "Book of Lessons" is Al-Baji, who in his book "Altakmil Alshaafi Lilghalil A'ala Kitāb Aleibur Li Abd Alrahman Bin Khaldun" (The Healing Completion of the Thirsty on the Book of Lessons for Abd Al-Rahman Ibn Khaldun) was interested in the nature of the relationship between the Khaldonian approach in historical studies and historical works in the Hafsid Period (1229-1574, A.D), (Al-Baji 2022: The "Introduction"), and who also in which tried to complement Kitab al-'Ibar "Book of Lessons", emulate it, and follow its approach (Al-Matwī 2012: 20-21).

According to Al-Baji, history is a science that is organized in a cultural project that is Islamic in source and traditional in view of the science of history at the heart of which the need to learn from the past and to encourage the consideration of and contemplation over past human experiences (Ibn Yusuf 1998: Vol. no.1: 6), and from this point of view, it does not differ that much from the classical view of history among Arabs and Muslims and the view of Ibn Khaldun himself of history, a view at the core of which is the need to take into thorough consideration the news of the past and its unfolded events (Ibn Tahir 2019: 50). And it should be noted that the interest in Ibn Khaldun and the passion for the "Introduction" spread strongly among the Al Husseini Court during the life of Al-Baji, who in turn was influenced by Ibn Khaldun and his vision of history (Ibn Tahir 2019: 50).

Sixth: Hamouda Ibn Abdulaziz (d: 1787-1788, A.D) and the "Al-Kitāb Al-Bāshī" (Book of Al-Bashi)

Hamouda Ibn Abdulaziz derived the news that is related to events that he did not witness from previous authors, especially Ibn Khaldun, when he transferred from him part of the chapter devoted to the Hafids (a Sunni Muslim dynasty of Berber descent who ruled Ifriqiya from 1229 to 1574). He also sought inspiration of several ideas in the context of his presentation of reality (Abdul Salam 1993: 298), and incorporated in his book Al-Bashi Ibn Khaldun's ideas with some intellectual independence, bypassing the cyclical view of time held by Ibn Khaldun, in order to highlight his progressive ideas, especially valuing the present time (Haniyeh 2018: 50).

Seventh: Abu Ras Al-Nasser Al-Maaskari (1751-1823, A.D) And the Revival of the Khaldounian Approach

Abu Ras sought to establish the principles of the science of history through the views of Ibn Khaldun, and his history was a mirror reflecting the socio-cultural decline that characterized the Arab Maghreb and the Islamic World for a long time (Abu Ras, "Zahr Al Shamarikh Fi Eilm Al Taarikh" (The Flower of Al-Shamarikh in the Science of History) [d.n]: 3). Abu Ras was called the "Protector of the Maghreb". In his historical books, Abu Ras relied primarily on the al-`Ibar Kitab "Book of Lessons" of Ibn Khaldun, and his benefit from Ibn Khaldun was not limited to benefiting from his history, but he was a debater and commentator on his views (Abu Ras, "Zahr Al Shamarikh Fi Eilm Al Tarikh" (The Flower of Al-Shamarikh in the Science of History) [d.n]: 5), and despite Ibn Khaldun's ingenuity in linking historical incidents with the socio-political input put forward by him in the eighth hijra century, and despite being distinguished by his insightful observations on the political, economic, and civilized society of his era, his school, however, did not find an echo among the historians of the ninth hijra century in Algeria (Abu Ras, "Zahr Al Shamarikh Fi Eilm Al Tarikh" (The Flower of Al-Shamarikh in the Science of History) [d.n]: 7). Hence, the importance of Abu Ras in reviving Ibn Khaldun in his approach and theorizations, as he derived most of the news, he put across from him, and followed his example in dealing with topics (Abu Ras, "Zahr Al Shamarikh Fi Eilm Al Taarikh" (The Flower of Al-Shamarikh in the Science of History) [d.n]: 9).

Abu Ras wrote in genealogy "Al Wasai'l Fi Ma'erifat Al Qabai'l" (The Means of Knowing the Tribes), and "Murouj Al Dhahab Fi Nabthah Min Al Nasab Waman Intamaa Alaa Al Sharaf Wa Thahab" (The Meadows of Gold in a Summary of Lineage and Who Belonged to Honor and Left"), and he agreed with the doctrine of Ibn Khaldun, who considered "Sareeh Al-Nasab" (Straight Forward Lineage) as associated with Bedouinism for social and economic considerations (Abu Ras, "A'ajai'b Al Asfar Wa Latai'f Al Akhbar" (The Wonders of Travel and the Pleasantness of the Tidings) [d.n] p1: 27).

Therefore, we find him reviving genealogy that was revived by Ibn Khaldun (Abu Ras, "A'ajai'b Al Akhbar That Al Ta'asees Fima Waqa'e Aw Sawf Yaqa'e Lilmuslimeen Min Al Faranseyyeen" (The Wonders of News Based on What Happened or Will Happen to Muslims with Francis) [d.n]: 16).

Eighth: Ibn Khaldun and the Reformist Thinkers

The reformists of the Maghreb in modern times cited what Ibn Khaldun stated -in his "Introduction" about religious policy- in the statement of approval of the beneficial policy of Sharia, despite the different evidence, as Ibn Khaldun aimed to describe the historical development and not to advocate the optimal policy (Abdul Salam 1993: 112), and the reformists interpreted Ibn Khaldun's words in this context according to their mental tendencies (Abdul Salam 1993: 113).

1. Ibn Salamah (1801-1850)

Muhammad Ibn Al-Tayeb Ibn Ahmad Ibn Ali Ibn Salamah Author of the book "Al-Iqd Al-Munadhad Fi Akhbar Al Mushir Albasha Ahmad" (The Neatly Arranged Contract in the News of Marshal Pacha Ahmad), which he specified it to translate his master Bey Ahmad Pacha's work, and also in which he traced Minister Hamouda Ibn Abdulaziz in his book Al Bashi and introduced his history with a preface in which he alluded to the division of sciences and their definitions as if trying to align his work to be on a par with the "Introduction" of Ibn Khaldun (Abdul Wahab 2005: vol. no .2, Section 1: 547). The preface also deals with history in general, power, sovereignty, and various functions of the state and their characteristics, and with its expansion and some of its references, the preface draws attention to Ibn Khaldun with whom Ibn Salamah had no qualms comparing himself (Abdul Salam, 1993: 345). One of the attributes of Ibn Salamah was that he was very proud of the depth of his historical knowledge (Karim, 1988: Edition no. 29: 192). The importance of Ibn Salamah's book "Al-Iqd al-Munadhad" comes in understanding the development of reformist thinking and its first form at the level of terminology, idea, and Al Ijtihad (Independent reasoning by an expert in Islamic law, or the thorough exertion of a jurist's mental faculty in finding a solution to a legal question), based on the religious heritage and the Arab and international situations in facilitating the transformation at the level of ideas and the level of practical political life (Karim 1988: 192). Also with regard to the preface, it seems that he [Ibn Salamah, that is] prepared it in accordance with the methodology of the Arab historians in placing a long introduction at the beginning of their writings, where they discuss and reiterate the concept of history and its place in science (Karim 1988: 194).

The structure of the composition in the "Al-Iqd al-Munadhad" is deep and the general appearance contains a main pillar, which was represented by an important political action, according to which the defense subject was changed, and from which Ibn Salamah sided with the renewal side and this required him to make a theoretical presentation supporting his opinion (resulting in what we described in the introduction as 'Humor' and the representation of vision of life and the concept of history) (Karim 1988: 196). In other words, it is a view with holistic tendency, resulting from the process of defending this measure with direct translational, historical, and political arguments, which framed such a view, with their position as the subject of the conclusion, and the planning of the book, which is a reversed process of its deep structure, which is in turn an exact replica of the evolution of the thinking of Ibn Salamah (Karim 1988: 197). "Iqd Al-Munadhad" is a defense of the system, renewal, and the obligation of Muslims to borrow what benefits

them from non-Muslims, giving rise to a new vision, a realistic and enlightened philosophy in which a new concept of history and its function is presented (Karim 1988: 199). Ibn Salamah's call is for an objective survey of history with a view to achieve renewal, and therefore Ibn Salamah can be considered in "Iqd Al-Munadhad" as the father of Tunisian Reformist Thought (Karim 1988: 207).

2. Ibn Abi Al Dhiaf (1802-1874)

Ibn Abi Al Dhiaf belongs to the Tunisian Reformist School, which believed in the need to open horizons to face reality, and he went to great lengths to achieve advancement and achievement (Ibn Abi Al Dhiaf 1999 p1: 1). Ibn Khaldun's history and the Science of Human Settlements (Ekistics) that he produced are considered one of the most important tributaries of the concept of "Enchantment". Ibn Abi Al Dhiaf narrated the history of Tunisia from the conquest to the reign of Hammuda Pasha based on the history of Ibn Khaldun (Ibn Abi Al Dhiaf 1999 p.1: g). In the preface of his book, Ibn Abi Al Dhiaf declares the basic principle of "Lesson/Moral" on which he based his idea and call for reform that is based on a framework and theory that the Ancients sought to recite and the Modernists sought to philosophize (Ibn Abi Al-Dhiaf 1999, p1: 1). Ibn Abi Al-Dhiaf did not view history with a simple superficial perspective, but looked at it through a composite point of view that equips the historian with the tools of trials and error and positive measurement and emphasizes the moral importance of history for rulers (Ibn Abi Al-Dhiaf 1999 p1: 2). The definition of history and its benefits for Ibn Abi Al-Dhiaf confirms to us that he quenched his thirst for knowledge from the Khaldounian thought and sought to follow on his [Ibn Khaldun, that is] thought and footsteps; as he was not limiting himself to narrating events, but deliberately investigated them in order to reach the Khaldounian objective of "Observation and Investigation" (Ibn Abi Al-Dhiaf, 1999 p1: s-p), and through such Khaldounian thought, the dialectical relationship between history and reform became clear (Ibn Abi Al-Dhiaf 1999 p1: s). Ibn Abi Al-Dhiaf was a model for the Khaldounian historian and for the competencies that a historian must possess, as he represented the only exceptional case that benefited from Ibn Khaldun's "Introduction" and the elements of his political stance and he also represented a method to criticize the tidings (Abdul Salam 1993: 529).

3. Mahmoud Qabadu (1815-1871, A.D)

Some Tunisian scholars called him the "African Genius" (Abdel Wahab 2005, vol. II, section I: 362). Qabadu represented a modern intellectual trend that came into existence as a result of the friction between the Islamic mindset and the Western mentality, from which a real intellectual doctrine emerged, which **"[h]as its original theories, basic rules, and abstract trends that depict things and their essence for what they really are."**(Ibn Ashur 1956: 14). One of Qabadu's means of reform was poetry, in which he preached on the means of progress, and on his call for reform, in which he included his socio-political poetry, that called for keeping up with the West in science, arts, and industries (Hussein 2010: 105). Qabadu embraced the method of Systematic Reincarnation and through Ibn Khaldun and his intellectual achievement a basis was provided for continuing the extension of this heritage based on the dictionary of Ibn

Khaldun's techniques and the rules of his urban science, and "*[since Justice was a prerequisite for the commencement of urbanization, and a covenant for the succession of man, it was necessary that it is fortified].*" (Qabadu 1951: 23).

4. Khair Al-Din Al-Tunisi (1820-1890 A.D)

Khair Al-Din Al-Tunisi, Prime Minister of the Beylik of Tunis and the Grand Vizier of the Ottoman Empire, wrote his book "Aqwam Al-Masālik Fī Ma'rifat Aḥwāl Al-Mamālik" (The Surest Path to Knowledge Regarding the Condition of Countries) in the nineteenth century, which was the century of great transformations, and the impact of Ibn Khaldun on him was evident in the sense that he wanted the introduction of his book to be on a par with the "Introduction" of Ibn Khaldun, whose influence was also evident from the first line in the book, and how Al-Tunisi cited several paragraphs and views of Ibn Khaldun he included in his introduction (Al-Tunisi 2012: 50). Khayr Al-Din Al-Tunisi wrote his book in the belief that he would do for the modern age what Ibn Khaldun did for an earlier age (Al-Hourani 1994: 113). Ibn Khaldun and Khair Al-Din shared the fact that they were both Tunisians, each of whom authored their books in a period of isolation from political life, and each of them methodically addressed the issue of the emergence and collapse of states, and each of them divided their book into an introduction to present the general principles and into several sections. Ibn Khaldun was mainly interested in the history of the Islamic State, while Khair Al-Din was interested in the history of European countries and their political and military systems (Al-Hourani 1994: 114).

5. Mohammad Bayram V (1840-1889, A.D)

The interest in political thought among some thinkers of nineteenth-century modernism is included as the cultural outcome generating reformist thought (Al-Badawi 1993: 9). Muhammad Bayram Al-Tunisi was an icon in holding the highest of thoughts (Yusuf 1890: vol. no.1, 498). He was the author of his book "Şafwat Al-l'tibār Bi-Mustawda' Al-Amşār Wa-Al-Aqṭār" (Elite Consideration in the Warehouse of Regions and Countries), and he intended to complete it as he was in the process of making its conclusion resembles in tone and tenor the "Introduction" of Ibn Khaldun and the book "Aqwam Al-Masālik Fī Ma'rifat Aḥwāl Al-Mamālik" (The Path to Knowing the Conditions of Kingdoms) (Bayram V. 1995 p1: 23). In Al-Safwa (The Elite) book, Bayram documented his journey in several European countries, a journey in which he depended on reconciling and mixing the provisions of the Islamic Sharia with the returns and the present provisions (Yusuf 1890: vol. no.1: 498). Bayram's goal in writing his book was to lay the foundations of a reform project that requires reforming the Islamic State and drawing up a plan for its prosperity (Bayram V. 1995 p1: 23). Şafwat Al-l'tibār book deals with history and its conclusion, and in which it shows how to fix the situation and bring back "the age of youth to Islam." (Al-Hourani 1994: 138).

6. Mohammed Al-Senussi (1851-1900)

We note that Tunisian historians from the seventeenth to the nineteenth century, belong to an epicenter that has its own distinctive features that indicate that they are a remnant of the Hafsīd era. It should be noted that the Tunisians did not receive a copy of the

"Introduction" that is until Ali Pacha, who ruled from (1735-1756), and who brought a copy from Fez, and since that time, the utilization of his history began through the enrichment of modern Tunisian histories with material on the history of intermediate Maghreb, in addition to linking the narrative of events with general observations on the connection of politics with economic and social conditions (Abdul Salam 1993: 523-524). Al-Senussi cited Ibn Khaldun in the course of his criticism of the tradition practiced by the Orientals as an extension from Western civilization, such as Ibn Khaldun's words about the enthusiasm of the defeated to imitate the victor in his/her circumstances and conditions. Al-Senussi repeatedly cited the "Introduction" and drew from its theorizations to explain what he witnessed on his trip to Europe (Abdul Salam 1993: 490). Ibn Khaldun's work in the "Introduction" contained philosophical principles that appeared when he presented the basic characteristics of human civilization and therefore, he deduced two basic points for the emergence of societies and civilizations: (Society is a necessity for human life), and (Human society that is based on cooperation in order to provide the elements of life and the defense of individuals, must be subject to political force) (Ibn Khaldun 2007: 40). Historians have drawn on these philosophical principles in the modern Arab renaissance era, including Muhammad Al-Senussi in the Hijaz journey, **"[since I understood the virtue of socialization, and realized the secret of God in cooperation to attract benefit.]"** (Al-Senussi 1979: 40).

Ninth: Interpretation of Islamic History from the Khaldounian Science of Dominion Ahmad Ibn Khalid Al-Salawi (1835-1897, A.D)

Al-Salawi emphasizes the importance and usefulness of history and its value, as the **"[virtue of the science of history is well-known, and its usefulness is great and serious.]"** (Al-Salawi 1954 p1: 6). Al-Salawi did not limit himself to using Ibn Khaldun as a source for him, but the influence of the latter's approach was clear in interpretation, analysis, and criticism, and his influence was evident in the former's explanation of the reasons for the Al Khurooj (Rebellion) against Uthmān ibn Affān (Third Caliph to rule after the death of the Prophet Muhammad), may Allah be pleased with him. And many researchers and historians did not realize the economic, social, and political transformations that took place during the reign of Uthman, **"[specifically when the living conditions became difficult during the time of Uthman, and when some people, who did not have a firm grounding in jurisprudence and religion and were not part of the "Ahl Al Sabiqah/Ahl al-Fatrah" (The people who lived during a gap in revelation between the times of the prophets Jesus (Isa) and Muhammad, approximately between 30 CE and 610 CE), or part of the honorable companions and Muslims, started becoming hostile against Uthman accusing him of neglecting the people and going against the life-history of "Al-Omarayn]" (Abu Bakr Siddiq and Umar Ibn Al-Khattab) (First and second Rashidun Caliphs after the death of the Prophet Muhammad, respectively)"** (Al-Salawi [d.n], p1: 20). After Al-Salawi got to the root of the problem, his approach, which was influenced by the author of the "Introduction", was manifested by explaining the reasons for the rebellion against Uthman, which were the non-conformity of the prevailing circumstances with the nature

of dominion, "*[and what they imagined of his neglect of the people until living conditions became difficult for them, in addition to everything else that was imagined, was all non-valid, as all of this was not under his control nor was it because of him, but due to the nature of human urbanization that causes such a thing, as a result of the regions, kingdoms, countries, areas, and cities that became part of the Islamic state and how the collected taxes were limited, in spite of the succession of the spoils of treasures of Khosrow (The Sasanian King of Kings of Iran from 531 to 579) and Caesar(a Roman general and statesman), and others, and despite all of that, and despite of the conquests and victories, things did not change, when it was said that "Nothing Lasts Forever!"]*". (Al-Salawi [d.n] p1: 20).

Tenth: Ibn Khaldun in the Lexicon of Translations (As a Model)

Mohammad Ibn Ahmad Al'ikrāry (d. 1939)

The authors of the books of classes and translations gave Ibn Khaldun and his Kitab al-'Ibar "Book of Lessons" and his famous "Introduction" an exceptional value as a model of seriousness, a book that was verified by Muhammad ibn Ahmad Al-Hudaiki (1775, A.D) (Al-Saidi 2008: 66), in his book "Tabaqat Al-Hudhaiki" (Classes/Layers of Al-Hudaiki) with a detailed translation (Al-Hudaiki [d.n] p1: 530-532).

Al'ikrāry praised Ibn Khaldun's Kitab al-'Ibar "Book of Lessons" in his book "Rawdat Alafinan Fi Safarat Alaeiani, Wakhbar Aleayni, Watakhtit Ma Fiha Min Eajib Albunyan" (Al-Afnan Kindergarten in the Deaths of Notables, News of the Spring, and a Map of the Marvelous Structures in It) (Al-Saidi 2008: 67-68). Al'ikrāry quoted and cited Ibn Khaldun's theories in his introduction (Al'ikrāry1998: 90, 191), and Al-Saidi concluded that Al'ikrāry, as a maker of individual human translations, created a relationship with a human gathering that he ended up translating, which was what famously compelled him -when he encountered social phenomena- to beg Ibn Khaldun, who was famous among the scientific-political elite and others, to create the "Ilm Al-Omran" (Science of Dominion). Therefore, it is inevitable to adopt it as a source of understanding and confirmation of interpretation, and this was what Al'ikrāry created (Al-Saidi 2008: 69).

Eleventh: Ibn Khaldun and the Renewal of Education

Mohammad Al-Mokhtar Al Soussi (d. 1963)

Al Soussi wrote the Encyclopedia of "Al-Ma'soul" (The Honeyed One) and his prolific production allowed the discovery of Ibn Khaldun in his details, and we see a great investment by him in reading, awareness, quotation, criticism, evaluation, and methodology (Al-Saidi 2008: 70). Ibn Khaldun's influence is also reflected in Al-Soussi in his educational methodology, which is represented in his book "Mira'at Al Tasrif" (The Mirror of Management" and its manuscript referred to the field of Education taken care of by Ibn Khaldun through consideration and reflection, which enriched his embodied perspective of Islamic education during his era and before his time, especially what related of it to criticizing some of his innovations such as exaggeration in abbreviation, explanation, and creating annotations (Al-Saidi 2008: 70). This perspective seems to be

influenced by Ibn Khaldun's theories to the greatest extent possible (Al-Saidi 2008: 70). The aim of Al Soussi's book "Mira'at Al Tasrif" (The Mirror of Management) was to try to apply this new perspective. Ergo, Al-Soussi is an enthusiast of Ibn Khaldun's project to reform the Islamic educational field during the Middle Ages and beyond (Al-Saidi 2008: 71). Al-Soussi was also inspired by Ibn Khaldun's perspective on the codification of genealogy (Al-Saidi 2008: 71).

Twelfth: The Life of "Umran" (Civilizational Thought) and its Continuity

1. Malek Ibn Nabi (1905-1973)

Ibn Khaldun, with the multiple contents of his "Introduction", still allows for many interpretations to date (Châtelet 1997: 13), and Malek Ibn Nabi got acquainted with Ibn Khaldun through the French translation made by leading French Orientalist "Silvestre de Sacy", the results of which were very significant for his thinking, as he stated in the "Mudhakirat Shahid Lilqarn" (Memoirs of A Witness of the Century" (Ibn Nabi, Memoirs of A Witness of the Century 1984: 113).

Many researchers believe that Malek Ibn Nabi represents the natural extension of the "Civilizational Thought", but on different conditions than the ones lived by Ibn Khaldun. And through his more-than-twenty authored books, Malek Ibn Nabi employed the concepts of Ibn Khaldun in the language of the era of the time, as it is the case in the concept of "Al Da'awah Al Deneyyiah" (Religious Calling), or "Al Wazi'e Al Dini" (Religious Deterrent), which was mentioned in the "Introduction" in several places and which turned into a "Fikrah Diniyyiah" (Religious Idea) in the texts of Ibn Nabi, and the same can be said apropos the concept of "Al Asabiyyah" (Tribalism), which turned into "Shabakat Al Ealaqat Al Iajtima'eiahi" (Network Of Social Relations". Ibn Nabi did not only quote and cite Ibn Khaldun, but he also criticized some of his propositions, where in his books "Shurut Al Nahdah" (Renaissance Terms) (1948) and "Wijhat Al A'alam Al Islamize" (The Destination of the Islamic World) (1954), some particulars of criticism were directed at the Khaldounian proposition in the interpretation of the movement of civilization, and considered his view incomplete due to his focus on the concept of the state as a unit of analysis of human society (Machouche 2012: 51).

Malek Ibn Nabi considered Ibn Khaldun as the first reference for Arab Sociology in the Middle Ages (Ibn Nabi, "Mushkilut Al Thaqafah" (The Problem of Culture) 1984: 20).

In his analysis of the picture of economic relations in the world in his book "Al Muslim Fi A'alam Al Iqtisad" (The Muslim in the World of Economics), Bennabi compared the economic development in the West, which has become a fundamental pillar of social life, and a fundamental law for regulating it, with the economy in the Islamic World, which remained in the stage of natural and unregulated economy. In the context of these boundaries, Ibn Nabi emphasized Ibn Khaldun's civilizational role that is unique in its exceptional consideration in addressing the impact of economic factors in history. However, Ibn Nabi's theory remained just that, written theoretical words in the Islamic Culture until the end of the twentieth century, that is (Ibn Nabi 1987: 16).

Mohammad Ibn Abdullah Al-Othmani (1984)

In his book "Alwāḥ Jazūlah Wa-Al-Tashrī' Al-Islāmī" (The Tablets of Gzoula and Islamic Legislation), Al-Othmani examines customs and their relationship to religion and morality, and the importance of this is in the social examination and the showing of the points of strengths and weaknesses of society (Al-Othmani 2017: 13), and we also encounter in this book the pattern of receiving for Ibn Khaldun and its influence in it (Al-Saidi 2008: 75), and in another place of the book, Al-Othmani drew from Ibn Khaldun his theory in imitation and employed it in analyzing some of the emergencies of the Sousse society in particular and the Moroccan one in general, regarding the steady social transformations in it (Al-Saidi 2008: 77).

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